
EFFECT OF CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY ON FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF INDUSTRIAL GOODS FIRMS IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study determined the effect of corporate social responsibility on financial performance of industrial goods firms in Nigeria. Specific objectives include to: determine the effect of corporate social responsibility costs on return on capital employed of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria and ascertain the effect of corporate social responsibility costs on return on assets of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. Ex Post Facto research design was adopted for the study. A sample of twelve industrial goods firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group was used. Data were extracted from the annual reports and accounts of these firms from 2013 to 2022. The study employed the panel regression model in a bid to determine the association between CSR and financial performance. The results obtained from the study revealed that corporate social responsibility costs have not significantly affect return on capital employed of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria; corporate social responsibility costs have significantly affect return on assets of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. Based on the findings, the study recommended among others that firms in Nigeria are yet to significantly use CSR to promote their performances like what is done by firms in developed economies.

Keywords: Corporate social responsibility, financial performance and Industrial goods firms

Introduction

Corporate social responsibility (CSR) encompasses the expectancies or now and again the philanthropic gesture that the society expects from the business businesses at a given factor in time (Nangih, 2022). They represent investments made via corporate bodies to better the society wherein they operate. Those they do by way of manner of donations, provision of basic infrastructures, embarking on advocacy campaigns, and other activities, so that you can ensure that they perform effectively and unhindered whilst making earnings to preserve the interest in their traders and different stakeholders.

Corporate social responsibility construct, advocates that, corporations like production corporations whose performance affect the environment without delay are more or much less impacting negatively the environment as observed by Lo and Sheu (2007). Many stakeholders clamor for a corporate social responsibilities practice so that you can meet their numerous wishes. Firm incurring social responsibility value is visible as developmental stride that seeks to compensate the community and other stakeholders for the damages as a result of corporations' monetary activities (Yahya & Ghodratollah, 2014). a few scholars opined that corporate social responsibility practices are a sustainable development strategy that seeks to attain societal wellbeing and equity even as, at the identical time, pursuing economic advantage (Ijeoma, 2015). Amacha & Dastane, 2017; Erhirhie & Ekwueme, 2019), posit that company social responsibility is vast, and a controversial idea that balances the need for monetary growth with society safety and social justice. Ajide and Aderemi (2014), opined that company social obligation wondering encourages groups to lessen their terrible impacts and decorate their fantastic influences on stakeholders. Some of global traits in enterprise exercise in 21st century economic system had been referred to within the paintings of Amacha and Dastane (2017) as authority's guidelines, pressures from applicable stakeholders like investors, clients, personnel, local groups, regulators and non-governmental organizations. Firms on their element are getting aware about the sustained long time significance and blessings of embracing sustainable commercial enterprise practice. Corporations also are under increasing stress to illustrate sturdy economic overall performance and advantageous socio-environmental affects (Eccles, Ioannou & Serafeim, 2012).

Alternatively, business entities cannot be sustained except they make profit. Arguably, the more profit they make in large part determines how well and how long they're going to ultimate inside the marketplace, in the midst of stiff opposition and ever-increasing marketplace complexities. An entity's earnings after tax, typically used as a degree of monetary overall performance, is regarded as the profit after the deduction of all known fees. It's a measure which exhibits the company's capacity to generate positive net earnings after the price of all charges referring to the length (Nangih, Onuora & Ofor, 2020).

Prior studies have explored and established that corporate social responsibility practices have a link with firm performance. For instance, Usman (2018) studied the association between corporate social responsibility and profitability of quoted banks in Nigeria. The study sampled 14 quoted banks from 2006 to 2015, and the findings showed that corporate social responsibility had significant and positive effect on profitability. The study by Ibrahim and Hamid (2019) assessed the effect of CSR on firm performance of listed companies in the non-financial services sector in Nigeria and found out that CSR investments had positive impact on firm performance. Kiabel and Nangih (2018) looked at the effect of effective policing on financial performance of selected oil and gas companies in Nigeria, and discovered that that peace and effective community policing influenced the profitability of oil

and gas companies positively. Again, Oboreh and Arukahoha (2021) studied the influence of corporate social responsibility on performance firms using listed in Nigeria and discovered a positive and significant link between CSR and performance companies. From the foregoing, none of these prior studies conducted research on industrial goods firms in Nigeria, thereby create a sectorial gap. This study however sought to fill the gap by carrying out research on corporate social responsibility costs and financial performance of listed industrial firms in Nigeria.

The main objective of this study is to examine corporate social responsibility costs and financial performance of industrial goods firms in Nigeria. Specific objectives include to:

1. Determine the effect of corporate social responsibility costs on return on capital employed of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria.
2. Ascertain the effect of corporate social responsibility costs on return on assets of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

Conceptual Review

Corporate Social Responsibility

The notion of corporate social responsibility (CSR) has been characterised in various approaches international, with both parallels and variances (Crane, Matten, and Spence, 2008; Uadiale & Fagbemi, 2012). CSR is described as figuring out, measuring, monitoring, and reporting an employer's social and financial effects on society, according to a file posted by way of Baker, Kumar, and Pattnaik (2020). It's far the public revelation of costs and return that may or won't be quantifiable in financial performance, however are borne disproportionately by using stakeholders and the general public due to organisations' monetary activity (Lee, 2021). CSR, consistent with Cuesta-Valiño, Rodríguez, and Núñez-Barriopedro, (2019), is an employer's function and operations about its perceived societal or stakeholder obligation.

Corporate social responsibility has no single usually universal definition as the concept is a fuzzy one with doubtful obstacles (Adam & Zutshi, 2004). It generally refers to business practices based totally on ethical values; with appreciate to people, communities and the surroundings (Ameer & Othman, 2012). Lin, Chang and Dang (2015), defined social responsibilities as the lengthy variety dreams of an company necessarily targeted upon its contributions to the desires of society's tangible or intangible, its contribution can be in terms of products or offerings or each. Once more, Adam and Zutshi (2004) asserted that social duty as control's selections and actions taken for reasons at the least partially past the corporation's direct monetary or technical hobby. Okegbe and Egbunike (2016) defined social reasonability as the obligation of corporate management to take moves and improve the welfare of the society which the organization does commercial enterprise that is to say further to their economic and legal duties, additionally they owe the society a few responsibilities.

For conscientious business executives to adopt corporate social obligation (CSR), it have to be phrased to encompass the complete range of enterprise responsibilities. Consistent with the literature, comprehensive CSR comprises 4 social responsibilities: economic, legal, moral, and philanthropic. In addition, those 4 CSR components or classes are probably proven as a pyramid (Kusyk, (2021). Kusyk (2021) argues that an idea of social duty, to definitely address the wide spectrum of responsibilities enterprise has to society, must move beyond the law and encompass the financial, criminal, moral, and discretionary dimensions of enterprise fulfillment. The idea that the organization has the most effective economic and legal responsibility however additionally moral and discretionary (philanthropic)

responsibilities became blanketed in a four-component theory of CSR (Kim, Milliman, and Lucas, 2020).

Firm Performance

Corporate performance has come to be a relevant idea in strategic control research and is often used as a based variable. Although it is a very not unusual belief within the academic literature, there's rarely a consensus approximately its definition and dimension (Saeed, 2013). Taouab and Issor (2019) indicates that the company performance as a fulfillment or effects obtained through management, economics, and marketing in supplying competitiveness, efficiency, and effectiveness to the corporation.

From an accounting literature attitude, firm overall performance hinge on organization profitability and overall performance of shares in the capital marketplace. The measures of company performance based on literature may be widely labeled into two particularly the market-orientated measures and the accounting- oriented measures. A properly acting firm can bring excessive and long-time period profits, with the intention to generate employment possibilities and enhance the profits of individuals. Moreover, financial profitability of a firm will enhance the returns of its employees, have better production gadgets, and bring products of better satisfactory for its clients. This procedure cannot be possible without an outcome size (Hailab, 2014).

Return on Assets (ROA)

ROA gives profitability on assets of the firm after meeting all expenses and taxes. It measures the profit of the firm after tax for each dollar invested in assets (Horne & Wachowicz 2005). It is an indicator of managerial performance. So, higher value of this ratio means better managerial performance (Ross, Westerfield & Jaffe 2005).

Emekewue (2008) sees return on assets (ROA) as a ratio which seeks to measure the amount of profit generated from the entire assets of the firm. It is express as Profit before tax Total Assets Ekwe and Duru (2012) opines that return on assets (ROA) was used as dependent variables, because it is an indicator of managerial efficacy. Return on assets (ROA) is a dependent variable. It is the quotient of dividing profit after tax by total assets. Lazaridis and Trynidis (2006), Falope and Ajilore (2009), Singh and Pandey (2008) and Karaduman et al (2011) agree that the formula for return on Assets (ROA) is expressed as Profit before tax over Total Assets.

ROA can be increased by increasing profit margin or asset turnover.

ROA = Net Profit / Total Assets.

Return on Capital Employed

The goal of financial management is to maximized investors economic welfare as reflected by management performance. Organizations aim at maximizing shareholders' wealth and generate enough profit to continue the business and to grow higher in future. Suffice to say that performance of firms is affected by multiple external and internal factors. The external factors include market preferences and perceptions, country rules and regulations, and economy of the country. The market and laws are same for similar businesses but different across industries, while internal factors are fundamental variables which are specific to firms such as Return On equity (ROE), Earning per Share (EPS) Return on Capital Employed, (ROCE), Market value per share (MVPS), Net Assets Value per share (NAVPS) Liquidity Ratio (LR) etc (Madugba & Okafor, 2016). The financial performance variables that will be considered in this study are: Return on capital employed, Earnings per share and Dividend per share. Also Bank age as a control variable will be considered. ROCE shows that the

company has been able to improve efficiency in the use of funds and capital. ROCE seeks to ascertain the level of profit made by a firm as a going concern (Emekaekwue, 2002). According to him, ROCE is calculated thus: $ROCE = (\text{Profit before interest and taxes} - \text{Income from external investment}) / (\text{Share capital} + \text{debt} + \text{reserve} - \text{External Investment})$ (Madugba & Okafor, 2016).

Empirical Review

Various studies have attempted to examine the impact of Corporate Social responsibility on financial performance. Olorunnisola and Usman (2023) investigated the effect of corporate social responsibility on market value of selected sectorial industries in Nigeria. Descriptive statistics, correlation regression panel and cross sectional analysis was adopted for the purpose of this study. The result showed that return on asset (ROE) has a positive correction = 0.4468 with return on equity (ROA) at 5 percent level of significant. Tobin Q has a positive relationship with ROA = 0.5321 and ROE = 0.0842 at 5 percent level of significant respectively. CSR has a negative relationship with ROA = -0.0948*, ROE = -0.0760 and Tobin Q = -0.0734 at 5 percent level of significant respectively. The findings revealed that firms in Nigeria are yet to significantly use CSR to promote their performances like what is done by firms in developed economies. Onodi, Ifedigbo and Onyemaechi (2022) ascertained the effect of corporate social obligation charges on financial overall performance of indexed production companies in Nigeria. The panel (simple) regression version was adopted for evaluation of records from twelve (12) companies that had been randomly selected from 2015 to 2020 (six years period). Findings from the study discovered that, corporate social responsibility cost has a positive insignificant impact on profits consistent with percentage of indexed companies in Nigeria. The study further revealed that; corporate social responsibility price has a high quality extensive impact on internet profit of listed corporations in Nigeria. Yakubu, Dangana, Olaifa and Afolayan (2022) examined the effect of corporate Social responsibility on financial performance of selected quoted companies in Nigeria. The study makes use of regression as a device for evaluation. The study suggests that company Social duty has a tremendous extensive effect on economic overall performance of quoted decided on firms in Nigeria. Oboreh and Arukaroha (2021) examined the effect of corporate social responsibility on performance of corporation, the usage of quoted groups in Nigeria because the reference point. The study analyzed statistics sourced from 2020 annual reviews and money owed of the respective organizations using descriptive statistics and easy linear regression. The study found that, company social duty expenditure of the businesses studied has enormous impact on return on property, go back on fairness and net profit margin.

Lyu, Wang, Zhang and Ng (2021) evaluated the effect of corporate social responsibility (CSR) on economic performance in hospitality enterprise in China. The study employed both quantitative and qualitative content analysis methods and become anchored at the stakeholder concept. The study confirmed that majority of the studies agreed that there exists positive correlation among CSR and financial performance. The study overview additionally confirmed that bad institutions exist among CSR and performance of samples of corporations making losses. Syder, Ogbonna and Akani (2020) examined the impact of company social obligation accounting document on shareholder cost of quoted oil and fuel businesses in Nigeria. The study employed the go-sectional and *Ex-Post Facto* research designs. the use of an Autoregressive allotted Lag (ARDL) certain check, descriptive statistic, model estimations and diagnostic analysis as well as a couple of regressions, the study determined that worker education and community improvement expenses had fantastic and massive effect on shareholder price added of the businesses. Ejike (2019) investigated disclosure of corporate social responsibility and monetary performance of public limited corporations in Nigeria.

CSR become measured in terms of key phrases on the annual reviews of selected corporations over five years starting from 2008-2012, at the same time as the economic overall performance of the companies became measured as return on belongings (ROA), Tobin's Q, and total shareholder return (TSR). Linear regression was executed at the information to validate the effect of CSR disclosure at the monetary performance of companies. Findings discovered that there exists no considerable impact of CSR disclosure at the monetary performance, each in short-run and lengthy-run for the selected public restrained companies in Nigeria. Ibrahim and Hamid (2019) assessed CSR and firm performance of indexed businesses within the non-monetary zone of Nigeria. The study the quasi-experimental research layout and made use of secondary sourced from annual reports of firms to purposively sample 23 firms for a period of ten years from 2008 to 2017. The data collected were subjected to analysis. The results confirmed that CSR had a considerable, however high-quality impact on monetary overall performance. It turned into concluded in the study that CSR investments can affect the economic overall performance of listed entities in Nigeria. Gugong and Ayuba (2018) studied nexus between CSR and company overall performance of listed companies in Nigeria. The examine duration changed into from 2008-2017. Regression analysis became used to analyze the facts. The study concluded that CSR on education and fitness have been significant and wonderful on economic overall performance, whereas the CSR on network and employee were poor but widespread on financial performance of the indexed patron goods firms in Nigeria.

Maqbooln & Aligarh (2018) investigated the relationship among corporate social responsibility and monetary performance in the Indian context. Secondary information had been accrued for 28 Indian commercial banks listed in Bombay inventory exchange (BSE) from 2007 to 2016. Their outcomes indicated that company Social responsibility exerts positive impact on financial overall performance of the Indian banks. Khan and Tariq (2017) studied the impact of corporate social obligation on monetary overall performance in Islamic and traditional banks of diverse Asian nations. Secondary data have been gathered from respective banks annual reviews. Correlation and regression techniques were employed. The findings of the study confirmed a usual nice and tremendous dating among corporate social responsibility and monetary performance. Han, Kim and Yu (2016) studied the relationship between corporate social responsibility and financial performance in Korea. The study made use of Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) score to proxy CSR variables, while financial performance variable was proxy by Return on Equity (ROE) for listed firms on Korea Stock Market in the period 2008-2014. They conclude that the ESG disclosure scores in the Korea corporations showed diversified results. Particularly, the environmental responsibility performance revealed a negative relationship with financial performance, whereas the governance responsibility performance score revealed a positive association with financial performance. On the other hand, they did not find any statistically significant evidence of relationship between the social responsibility performance score and financial performance. Otu, Ejovwokeoghen and Morenike (2016) examined the Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) disclosure practices of Nigerian quoted companies and their determinants from 2013 to 2014. Data obtained were analyzed using descriptive statistics, correlation and regression. The result of their findings showed that CSR was influenced by company size and auditor type; but not by profitability. Ahmed, Zakaree, Oladele and Kolawole (2016) examined the impact of corporate social responsibility disclosure (CSR) on the financial performance of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Sample size of ten (10) manufacturing firms was drawn randomly from seven (7) subsectors of the Nigerian manufacturing industry. Secondary data were collected from the financial statements of the sampled firms and multiple regression analysis was employed. The result of the study showed

an overall significant positive association between CSR and EPS, all the four CSR dimensions (employee, environment, community and product) have significant positive effect on the EPS. Hossain, Chowdhury, Evan and Lema (2015) ascertained the association between corporate social responsibility and corporate financial performance: evidence from a developing country firms from 2008-2012. Legitimacy theory and stakeholder theory underpinned the study. The result of the study showed a positive and significant relationship between CSR and CFP but an insignificant relationship when using the market-based Tobin's Q. Jibril, Dahiru, Muktar & Bello (2016) determined the association between corporate social responsibility and financial performance of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria from 2008 to 2013. They adopted multiple regression technique in analyzing the data with the aid of SPSS techniques. The findings reveal that corporate social responsibility has a positive and significant impact on return on equity and return on assets as financial performance proxies of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Methodology

This study adopted *Ex Post Facto* research design. *Ex-post facto* means after the event, meaning that the events under investigation had already taken place and data already exist. This is appropriate because the study aims at measuring the existing data which are not manipulated. This involves use of financial accounts of organizations to generate the financial analysis that will determine the significant difference of the variables.

The population of the study consists of twelve (12) listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria, according to the Nigeria Exchange Group (2022), as at 31st December 2022. Since the population size is not large, the researcher used consensus sampling to adopt all the population for the study.

To obtain reliable information that will help the researcher to ensure the effectiveness of the study in question, data will be extracted from the annual reports and accounts of industrial goods firms in Nigeria 2013 to 2022. The variables include donation for independent variable, while return on equity, return on assets and profit margin of financial reports represent dependent variable, and firm size for the control variable.

Model Specification

The study adapts the model of Olorunnisola and Usman (2023) on the effect of corporate social responsibility index on firm performance in the selected sectorial industries in Nigeria.

$$FP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CSRDI_{it} + \beta_2 FSIZE_{it} + \beta_3 LEV_{it} + e_{it} \dots \dots (3.1)$$

Where,

FP = Financial performance include (ROE, ROA & EPS)

ROE= Return on Equity

ROA = Return on Asset

EPS = Earnings per share

CSRDI = Corporate social responsibility disclosure index

FSIZE = Firm Size

LEV = Leverage

e = Error Terms

The model was modified to suit the variables selected for this study, as follows

$$CSR_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ROE_{it} + \beta_2 ROA_{it} + \beta_3 NPM_{it} + \beta_4 LEV_{it} + \mu_{it}$$

Where:

CSR = Corporate social responsibility

ROA = Return on Asset

NPM = Net profit margin

LEV = Firm leverage

$\beta_0 - \beta_2$ = Slope Coefficients

i=ith Firm

t=Time Period

μ = Error Term

Method of Data Analysis

Data were analyzed with descriptive statistics, and the hypotheses will be tested with Pearson correlation, and multiple regression analysis. Since the focus of the study is to examine the effect of asset composition on financial performance, regression analysis becomes appropriate tool for it.

Descriptive statistics employed to summarily describe the mean, median, standard deviation, kurtosis and skewness of the study variables. Inferential statistics will also be utilized with the aid of E-Views 9 using:

- i. Coefficient of correlation: which is a good measure of relationship between two variables that tell us about the strength of relationship and the direction of the relationship as well?
- ii. Regressions analysis: Regression analysis predicts the value the dependent variable based on the value of the independent variable and explains the impact or effect of changes in the values of the variables.

Decision Rule

Accept the alternative hypothesis, if the Probability value (P-value) of the test is less than 0.05 (5%). Otherwise reject.

Data Analysis

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	DNT	ROCE	ROA	LEV
Mean	8546.200	-0.016496	-0.018625	0.136259
Median	5600.000	-0.004731	-0.004800	0.138159
Maximum	47546.00	0.043180	0.026822	0.230298
Minimum	0.000000	-0.096754	-0.082990	0.032253
Std. Dev.	14046.76	0.051880	0.041085	0.066734
Skewness	2.424575	-0.349092	-0.491941	-0.087588
Kurtosis	7.385802	1.741291	1.766121	1.965576
Jarque-Bera	17.81230	0.863254	1.037700	0.458634
Probability	0.000136	0.649451	0.595205	0.795077
Sum	85462.00	-0.164956	-0.186248	1.362590
Sum Sq. Dev.	1.78E+09	0.024223	0.015192	0.040081
Observations	10	10	10	10

Source: E-Views 9.0 Descriptive Output, 2024

Interpretation

Table 4.1 presents the descriptive statistics for the dependent variables, financial performance (ROCE, ROA,) and the independent variable donation (DNT), while firm leverage (LEV) formed the control variable. The mean serves as a tool for setting benchmark. The median re-ranks and takes the central tendency. While the maximum and minimum values help in detecting problem in a data. The standard deviation shows the deviation/dispersion/variation from the mean. It is a measure of risk, the higher the standard deviation, the higher the risk. The standard deviation is a measure that summarizes the amount by which every value within a dataset varies from the mean. It is the most robust and widely used measure of dispersion. The standard deviation in the firms various sectors for the period 2013-2022 is 14046.76, 0.052, 0.041, and 0.067 for ,DNT, ROCE, ROA, and LEV respectively. Skewness and

Kurtosis are contained in Jarque-Bera. Positively skewed is an indication of a rise in profit while negatively skewed is an indication of loss or backwardness. Jarque-bera is used to test for normality; to know whether the data normally distributed. Table 1 reveals that many of these variables are with probability values higher than 5%. So invariably, they are significantly normally distributed. While the probability values few are not significantly normally distributed because their probability values of are greater than 5%.

Correlation Analysis

In examining the association among the variables, we employed the Pearson correlation coefficient (correlation matrix) and the results are presented in table 2:

	DNT	ROCE	ROA	LEV
DNT	1			
ROCE	0.09489	1		
ROA	0.141029	0.99545	1	
LEV	-0.22857	0.26575	0.26778	1

The use of correlation matrix in most regression analysis is to check for multi-collinearity and to explore the association between each explanatory variable (DNT) and the dependent variables (ROCE, ROA, ROE). Finding from the correlation matrix table shows that all our independent variables, (ROCE=-0.095; ROA=0.141, and LEV =-0.229) were observed to be negatively associated with return on assets. In checking for multi-collinearity, we notice that no two explanatory variables were perfectly correlated. This means that there is no problem of multi-collinearity between the explanatory variables. Multi-collinearity may result to wrong signs or implausible magnitudes in the estimated model coefficients, and the bias of the standard errors of the coefficients.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One

Ho₁: Corporate social responsibility costs have no significant effect on return on capital employed of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

Table 3: Regression analysis between DNT, ROCE and LEV

Dependent Variable: ROCE

Method: Least Squares

Date: 04/14/24 Time: 13:58

Sample: 2013 2022

Included observations: 10

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-0.053806	0.046748	-1.150973	0.2875
DNT	6.07E-07	1.36E-06	0.444914	0.6698
LEV	0.235780	0.286941	0.821700	0.4383
R-squared	0.096183	Mean dependent var		-0.016496
Adjusted R-squared	0.162050	S.D. dependent var		0.051880
S.E. of regression	0.055925	Akaike info criterion		-2.686271
Sum squared resid	0.021894	Schwarz criterion		-2.595496
Log likelihood	16.43136	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-2.785852
F-statistic	0.372467	Durbin-Watson stat		0.972899
Prob(F-statistic)	0.701910			

Source: E-Views 9.0 correlation output, 2024

Interpretation of Regression Result

In table 3, a panel least square regression analysis was conducted to test the effect between corporate donation and return on capital employed. Adjusted R squared is coefficient of determination which tells us the variation in the dependent variable due to changes in the independent variable. From the findings in the table 3, the value of adjusted R squared was 0.26, an indication that there was variation of 26% on return on capital employed (ROCE) due to changes in corporate donation and firm leverage. This implies that only 26% changes in ROCE of the firm could be accounted for by ROCE and LEV, while 74% was explained by unknown variables that were not included in the model. The probability of the slope coefficients indicate that; $P(= 0.670; x_2= 0.438)$. The co-efficient value of; $\beta_1= 6.07$, and 0.24 for donations method and firm leverage implies that donations is positively related to return on capital employed though not statistically significant at 5%.

The linear regression model becomes;

The Durbin-Watson Statistic of 0.972899 suggests that the model does not contain serial correlation. The F-statistic of the donations regression is equal to 0.3724676 and the associated F-statistic probability is equal to 0.702, so the alternative hypothesis was accepted and the null hypothesis was rejected.

Since the Prob (F-statistic) of 0.702 is higher than the critical value of 5% (0.05), then, it would be upheld that there is no significant effect between corporate social responsibility and return on capital employed of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria at 5% level of significance.

Hypothesis Two

H_{02} : Corporate social responsibility costs affect have not significantly affect return on assets of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

Table 4: Regression analysis between DNT, ROA and LEV

Dependent Variable: ROA
 Method: Least Squares
 Date: 04/14/24 Time: 13:59
 Sample: 2013 2022
 Included observations: 10

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-0.050514	0.036637	-1.378771	0.2104
DNT	6.24E-07	4.07E-06	2.584191	0.0517
LEV	3.194888	2.224878	2.866639	0.0419
R-squared	0.314860	Mean dependent var		-0.018625
Adjusted R-squared	0.438037	S.D. dependent var		0.041085
S.E. of regression	0.243829	Akaike info criterion		3.173714
Sum squared resid	0.213447	Schwarz criterion		3.082939
Log likelihood	18.86857	Hannan-Quinn criter.		3.273295
F-statistic	4.454178	Durbin-Watson stat		1.145140
Prob(F-statistic)	0.015244			

Source: E-Views 9.0 correlation output, 2024

Interpretation of Regression Result

In table 4, a panel least square regression analysis was conducted to test the effect between corporate donation and return on assets. Adjusted R squared is coefficient of determination

which tells us the variation in the dependent variable due to changes in the independent variable. From the findings in the table 4, the value of adjusted R squared was 0.44, an indication that there was variation of 44% on return on assets (ROA) due to changes in corporate donation and firm leverage. This implies that only 44% changes in ROA of the firm could be accounted for by ROA and LEV, while 56% was explained by unknown variables that were not included in the model. The probability of the slope coefficients indicate that; $P(= 0.051; x_2= 0.041)$. The co-efficient value of; $\beta_1= 6.24$, and 3.19 for donations and firm leverage implies that corporate donations is positively related to return on assets and statistically significant at 5%.

The linear regression model becomes;

The Durbin-Watson Statistic of 1.145140 suggests that the model does not contain serial correlation. The F-statistic of the donations regression is equal to 4.454178 and the associated F-statistic probability is equal to 0.015, so the alternative hypothesis was accepted and the null hypothesis was rejected.

Since the Prob (F-statistic) of 0.015 is less than the critical value of 5% (0.05), then, it would be upheld that there is a significant effect between corporate social responsibility and return on assets of quoted industrial goods firms in Nigeria at 5% level of significance.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study focused on determining the nexus between CSR and financial performance of industrial goods firms in Nigeria; given the increasing attention of firms to the sustainability of the environments in which they operate. In furtherance of this overriding objective, the study specifically examined the effects of CSR on performance. The study employed the panel regression model in a bid to determine the association between CSR and financial performance. The results obtained from the study revealed that corporate social responsibility costs have not significantly affect return on capital employed of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria; corporate social responsibility costs affect have significantly affect return on assets of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. Consequently, industrial goods firms' that increase their commitments to corporate social responsibility are likely to enhance their profitability but not significantly. On the other hand, firms with greater managerial competences will significantly enhance financial performance.

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were stated;

1. The findings revealed that firms in Nigeria are yet to significantly use CSR to promote their performances like what is done by firms in developed economies. Therefore, as part of the recommendation from this study, Nigerian firms are advised to pay more attention to being CSR responsible and find ways by which this can translate to improved profit and enhancement of their overall performances.
2. Industrial goods firms should re-evaluate their social environmental strategy in order to ensure that they align with the firms' objectives; in a bid to ensure equitable returns to shareholders as well as significantly enhancing their long-term profitability.

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